

CENTRAL GREECE

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Main structure (feel free to expand)

1. Lessons learned
2. Main results achieved
3. Action Plan alignment and adoption
4. Pilot case study
5. Technical tools
6. Foresight tools (guides)

1. Lessons

Lessons learned

- Meetings with stakeholders provide a better understanding of factors that affect the regional development
- Engaging the stakeholders is very important, but it is a very challenging process (time, resources)
- Text mining and SDM provide an innovative approach to rural development, however, the end users may face difficulties due to limited digital skills

Recommendations

- Foresight processes provide significant potential to assist in Rural Development planning and get insights in how certain policy changes can influence the region

2. Results

Stakeholders Panel – 42 people

- 4% Scientific
- 29% Policy
- 15% Newcomers
- 52% Community

CENTRAL GREECE - STAKEHOLDER PANEL

2. Results

Stakeholder interactions

- 3 Foresight meetings – 35 people
- 3 SDM meetings – 37 people
- 2 meetings for updating the Regional Action Plan – 15 people
- Numerous one to one interactions
- Newspaper articles and Local TV podcast

2. Results

- Top priority needs and issues
- Policy scenarios and possible outcomes
- Investigate initiatives and financial options
- Finalise Mission / vision statement and Regional Action Plan
- Dissemination actions and engagement processes

2. Results

Mission

Introduction of new interventions focused on improvement of training opportunities and digital & innovation skills, especially in the agri-food sector (e.g. smart farming, ICT skills) and development of collaborations between regional/national actors to effectively exploit the many key regional strengths such as tourism.

2. Results

- Top priority needs and issues

Top Priority Needs	Key Barriers
Create sustainable jobs	Fragmented approaches and the need for structured and linked policies that are clearly perceived by those directly involved
Modernize the agri-food sector	Bureaucracy
Create better links between farming, food, and other sectors along the value chain (e.g. tourism)	Multiplicity of laws
Support the Digital transformation of rural life	Lack of political stability
Improve the quality of life for those who live here	Lack of Awareness
Optimise draw-down from major sources of EU funding CAP, Green Deal, Cohesion Funds	

2. Results

SDM

Central Greece Model v3

Show wizard Hide help Load defaults

Vocational training

Percentage of population finishing school and continuing to vocational training

70

Broadband coverage objective

Percentage of population to be covered by broadband after broadband campaign

66

Time to complete broadband campaign

Time to complete broadband campaign in years after 2023

0

Investment into entrepreneurship and innovation

Direct investments in € made into entrepreneurship targeted at companies and individuals

3. Action Plan alignment and adoption

3. Action Plan

Successful Adoption

- Meetings with regional policy makers and consultations with key organisations
- Explore funding options from the PoliRural Inventory and potential collaborations and synergies

Case study

Text Mining

- A large library of more than 4000 documents related to European rural areas.

Polirural Digital Innovation Hub

- Visualisation of Rural Attractiveness across Europe

Current Rural Situation Pilot Phase 1

- SWOT analysis
- Evaluation of policy measures
- Development of Roadmaps & Regional Action Plan

Foresight Activities Pilot Phase 2

- Inventory on drivers of change
- Sources of funding
- SDM

Regional Action Plans Pilot Phase 3

- Evaluation & Finalise Regional Action Plans
- Regional Recommendations

4. Case study

A word document and a presentation including information regarding Regional Action Plan, SDM, Text mining were translated in Greek in order to share it with stakeholders. A final event was held to evaluate and disseminate results and an article was published in the local newspaper

5. Tools (tech)

- **Regional SDM:** explore possible impact of different policies. It will be useful for other EU projects relevant to policy making
- **Semex:** AUA team will keep consulting it for a variety of research activities
- **Rural Attractiveness Explorer:** It can be used as a visual tool to support future policies
- **Digital Innovation Hub-Atlas of Best Practices:** It will be used to promote businesses

6. Tools (guides)

- **Guide to Deep Dives (Covid)**

This will be used to enable well-informed discussions on what has changed in the regional economy and in the organization of living and working during unexpected crisis

- **Guide to Deep Dives (CAP Reform)**

Share it with regional policy to provide more targeted support to smaller farms, and allow greater flexibility for adaptation of measures to local conditions.

- **Guide to Deep Dives (Green Deal)**

Share it with regional policy to put forward (legislative) measures focusing on energy transition, circular economy, sustainable transport, biodiversity and agriculture

6. Tools (guides)

- The STEEPV Inventory of Drivers of Change

As a reference methodology to gain better understanding of the rural areas

- D1.8 Future Outlooks Methodology:

As reference methodology for planning and implement Action Plans. It will be used for similar projects